

THE ROLE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOLK MEDICINE AND OFFICIAL MEDICINE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICINAL HERBAL MEDICINE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7810948>

ELSEVIER

Sayramov Fayzullo Baratjon o`g`li

Fergana State University, student of the joint faculty of Agriculture

Abstract: treatment of people and animals, prevention of diseases plants-herbs. There are 10-12 thousand species of medicinal plants on Earth. Chemical, pharmacological and medicinal properties of more than 1000 plant species have been investigated. There are 577 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. Of these, 250 species are currently used in scientific medicine. The effect of medicinal plants on the body depends on the amount of compounds in their composition. These compounds accumulate in different amounts in different parts of the plant. The necessary parts of the plant for the preparation of the drug are collected for different periods. For example, bark, bud are taken in early spring, leaf before or when the plant blooms, when the flowers are fully open, when fruits and seeds ripen, underground organs (roots, rhizomes and onions) are taken in early spring or late autumn.

Keywords: alkaloid, additives, folk medicine, essential oil, medicine, official medicine..

Received: 22-03-2023

Accepted: 22-03-2023

Published: 22-03-2023

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The acting substance of medicinal plants is alkaloids, various glycosides (anthroglucosides, glycosides affecting the heart, saponins, etc.), flavonoids, coumarins, additives and other mucous substances. Essential oils, vitamins, tar and other compounds can be present. Many plants are made with antibiotics and phytoncides-rich preparations that eliminate microorganisms and viruses. Closely related chemical compounds typical of the same group are found in the same family or order, while some chemical compounds may also be found in plants of different families that are not closely related.

Since ancient times, man has been using wild-growing plants in the treatment of various diseases.

In the current period, the variety of medicinal plants has increased, and folk medicine is enriched with healing plants.

Most of the medicinal plants used in scientific medicine are derived from plants that have been used by the people for centuries. Medicinal plants that are used in folk medicine cannot be used in scientific medicine. In Uzbekistan, more common medicinal plants are pomegranate, bitter, almond, medicinal rose, Walnut, jaw-jaw, zubtutum, bite, itsigek, lobster, pistachio tree, sage, choyut, cilantro, Shirin, shimmer, Wormwood, yantok, rubella, hookworm, etc. Alkaloids are obtained from bitter - pakhikarnin, garmin from isirik, anabazin from itsigek, galantamine from omonqora, spherophysin from shilirbosh. Pelterin tanat and

extract, driven by vomiting, are made from pomegranate peel. Medicinal preparations gulkhairi are used as a phlegm repellent and emollient, jaw-jaw and lagoxilus drugs as a bleeding suppressor, pistachio Angus and choyut drugs as a treatment for gastrointestinal diseases. 2 different descriptions of medicinal plants have been adopted:

1. Depending on the composition of the acting substances - alkaloid, glycosidic, essential oil, vitamin, etc;
2. Depending on its pharmacological indicators - sedative, analgesic, sleeping, as well as those that affect the cardiovascular system, stimulate the central nervous system, lower blood pressure and other medicinal plants.

In chemical and pharmaceutical factories in Tashkent, various medicines are prepared from medicinal plants grown and planted in Uzbekistan. For example, psoralen, which is used in the treatment of PES from the root and fruit of oqquray, rutin, which acts on vitamin A dek from the Japanese Sofora hump, galantamine alkaloid from Omani, strophantine from Kendor, simarin, cardiac glycosides and other preparations olina began. As mentioned above, currently, about 250 plant products are used in medicine. 48% of the products of the medicinal plants shown are made from wild-growing plants, 30% in the fields where medicinal plants are grown from farms located in different soil climates. The remaining 22% form a "mixed" group, that is, this group is collected from plants, where the product of medicinal plants grows both wild and on plantations. Then it is expected that the Salm of medicinal products made from the "mixed" group of medicinal plants will increase year after year in the amount of the total collected medicinal product.

For what reasons is the product of medicinal plants grown on irrigated areas increasing from the total amount of products prepared annually?

There are many reasons for this, the main ones being:

1. As a result of the growing need for the product of medicinal plants every year, the amount of preparation of their raw materials is also increasing. This, in turn, leads to the fact that a number of medicinal plants are reduced in a large area of growth, as a result of which the preparation of their raw materials is sharply limited or completely stopped.

As a result of the abundant preparation of the ground tops and onions of bozulbang and blackberries, which grow wild in Uzbekistan, their reserves (quantity) have greatly decreased in the place of natural growth. Therefore, at present, these plants are included in the "Red Book" of Uzbekistan. Therefore, the preparation of their natural raw materials at the place of growth has been stopped and is being grown in farm fields and in places where they grow themselves wild. Such examples can be cited in large numbers.

2. As a result of the increased demand for the product of medicinal plants on a regular basis and its non-satisfaction at the expense of wild-growing plants, it is necessary to grow these plants in irrigated regions.

3. Sometimes, when rare medicinal plants are in high demand, but they grow wild, in unfavorable places for collection (for example, belladonna, which grows in the mountainous districts of the Caucasus and Crimea, etc.) or in small quantities, scattered in large areas (for example, medicinal valeriana, which is common in the European part of Russia, but is rare, etc.), the preparation of Therefore, it is advisable to grow such plants in the fields of farms.

4. The challenge of large-scale preparation of raw materials of wild-growing medicinal plants is the complexity of using agricultural techniques to harvest it. The product of medicinal plants grown on the plantation can be harvested using various mechanisms in favorable conditions and during a period when an impressive amount of chemical biologically active substances is accumulated.

5. If a valuable, medically essential medicinal product is made from plants that grow in tropical or subtropical climates that are not found in our republic, it is advisable to grow these plants on our own whenever possible.

Agrotechnics of medicinal plants to be planted anew are being developed at VILR and its experimental stations, partly in the botanical gardens of the Academy of Sciences (FA), universities and higher educational institutions. In this area, the service of VILR and his experimental stations was large, in which the agrotechnical rules for growing several tropical and subtropical medicinal plants brought from abroad in the climate of the former Union were developed. On farms located in different regions (zones) of our country, the following medicinal plants are grown: xin tree, coca bush, aloe species, orthosiphon, dichroa, large kella, sano (cassia) species, Mexican bangidevona, kalankhoy species, shy mimosa, dark red passiflora, rauvolphia species, pink Catharanthus (bullfinch), round-leaved Stephania, eucalyptus species, spotted ituzum, etc.

Medicinal plants grown in irrigated areas are very different from medicinal plants grown wild, which means that the medicinal plant product grown does not contain a mixture of foreign plants. Medicinal plants grown according to agrotechnical rules will be fertile and rich in biologically active substances.

It is possible to increase the yield of medicinal plants and the amount of biologically active chemical compounds in their composition, which are planted by choosing fertile varieties of medicinal plants, their cross-breeding or obtaining varieties with polyploids (increasing chromosome numbers).

For the reasons mentioned above, the cultivation of some medicinal plants and the preparation of their products cost much more economically than the collection of the product of medicinal plants growing wild. In Uzbekistan, medicinal plants

are planted mainly on farms under the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management, which are located in different soil climatic regions.

For the first time in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1973, medicinal plants began to be planted on farms in the Bostanlık District of the Tashkent region. Later (in 1978) in the Pop District of Namangan region, a farm was established where medicinal plants called Ibn Sino were grown. In the fields of this farm, pepper mint, medicinal marmalade (sage), medicinal nail polish, naamatak, bitter wormwood (Armenian), lumpy ituzum, small-flowered mountain ash and other plants were grown. The products collected from them were shipped to Uzbekistan pharmacies and to Chimkent chemical and pharmaceutical plants and other enterprises.

Currently, Special farms for growing medicinal plants have been established in Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Surkhandarya and Tashkent regions.

Under the production associations of "Pharmacy" in almost all regions of the Republic, fields are created that grow medicinal plants, in which the region grows the appropriate plants at the request of pharmacies.

Currently, in the fields of a specialized farm named Okhunboboev, which specializes in medicinal plants in the Middle Chirchik District of the Tashkent region, pepper mint, medicinal marmarak (sage), medicinal nail polish, medicinal chamomile, five - lane ituzum-arslonkuyruq, pol-pola, na'matak and other medicinal plants are grown.

Former senior scientific officer of Tashkent botanical garden under the FA of the Republic of Uzbekistan Q. H. Khojaev, later head of the laboratory of cultural and climatic adaptation of Medicinal Plants of the same park, Senior Scientific Officer Yu. M. Murdakhaev, in cooperation with the scientific staff of the Departments of Pharmacognosy and Botany of the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, managed to grow 67 types of medicinal plants brought from the Fraternal republics and other regions of the world (regions) in the climate of the city of Tashkent. In their opinion, above the nail polish, pepper mint, medicinal marmalade (sage), medicinal valeriana, fennel (pharmacy ukropi), medicinal chamomile, black andiz, ajgon (zirai Carmoni), fennel, common dastarbosh, na'matak species, bushy amorpha, red angishvonagul, Sagittarius erizimum, hemp species, yamsi, man'chjuria Aralia, mountain jumrut, sano (cassia) species, patrinia, ovate, five-lobed lionfish, medicinal zangvizorba, semi-shrubby securinega, bullfinch species, scab species, Belladonna, Mexican bangidevona, Pol-Pola, spotted ituzum, it is possible to grow Gangetic buzulbang and other medicinal plants.

Currently, the reserves of medicinal plants growing naturally are decreasing under the influence of humans. In order to complement this and satisfy the needs of our people, it will be advisable to increase the types of medicinal plants and plant them in irrigated regions, taking into account the soil and climatic conditions

of Uzbekistan. In order to provide the pharmaceutical industry in Uzbekistan with raw materials of medicinal plants, it would be advisable to organize and increase farms and specialized farms that will plant and grow medicinal plants in the coming years.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Karimov V., Shomahmudov A. Folk medicine and modern science are healing plants that are used in medicine. - Tashkent, 1993.
2. Kursanov A. I. vagabonds. Botany Volume 2-Tashkent, 1963.
3. Mustafayev S.M. Botany-Tashkent, 2002.
4. Nabiyev M. Botanical atlas-dictionary. - Tashkent, 1969.
5. Nabiev M. Lechebniedarichatkala-Tashkent, 2004.
6. Oripov R.O, Khalilov N.X. Plant Studies-Tashkent, 2007.
7. Prator O.P, Nabiyev M.M. Modern plants of Uzbekistan High system-Tashkent, 2007.
8. Yusupova, Z. A., & Baratjon ogli, S. F. (2022). LABGULDOSHLAR OILASI VAKILLARINING HAYOTIY SHAKLLARI, MORFOLOGIYASI VA TARQALISHI. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 2(24), 472-479.
9. Yusupova, Z. A., & Baratjon o'g'li, S. F. (2022). LAMIACEAE OILASINING EFIR MOYIGA BOY BO'LGAN BAZI TURLARINING MORFOLOGIYASI. Scientific Impulse, 1(2), 692-695.
10. Yusupova, Z. A., & Baratjon o'g'li, S. F. (2022). BIOECOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF MEDICINAL SPECIES OF THE MINT FAMILY (LAMIACEAE). Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 10(11), 183-190.
11. Yusupova, Z. A., & Baratjon ogli, S. F. (2022). NATURAL MEDICINAL HERBS OF THE LAMIACEAE FAMILY AND THEIR MEDICAL PROPERTIES. JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, 2(13), 64-68.
12. Yusupova, Z. A., & Baratjon ogli, S. F. (2023). LIFE FORMS, MORPHOLOGY AND DISTRIBUTION OF REPRESENTATIVES OF LAMIACEAE FAMILY. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(1), 288-295.
13. Baratjon o'g'li, S. F. (2022). SPECIES OF THE LAMIACEAE FAMILY WITH SPICE PROPERTIES. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 10(11), 85-89.

14. Baratjon o'g'li, S. F. (2022). ПРИРОДНЫЕ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫЕ ТРАВЯНИСТЫЕ РАСТЕНИЯ ПРЕДСТАВИТЕЛЕЙ СЕМЕЙСТВА LAMIACEAE И ИХ ЛЕЧЕБНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(5), 1048-1055.

15. Yusupova, Z. A., & Baratjon ogli, S. F. (2023). ESSENTIAL OIL PRESERVATIVE CONTAINING TIMOL REPRESENTATIVES OF THE LAMIACEAE FAMILY. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 1(6), 104-108.

16. Yusupova, Z. A., & Baratjon ogli, S. F. (2023). LIFE FORMS, MORPHOLOGY AND DISTRIBUTION OF REPRESENTATIVES OF LAMIACEAE FAMILY. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(1), 288-295.

17. Baratjon ogli, S. F. (2023). Morphology, Chemical Composition and Medical Use of Ocimum Plant. *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 13, 5-8.

18. Yusupova, Z. A., Baratjon ogli, S. F., & Abduqunduzovna, M. Z. (2023). Medicinal Plants Growing in Our Republic Medicinal Properties. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 15, 5-7.